

MATHEMATICS LEARNING EXPERIENCES USING EDUCATIONAL VIDEOS AND THE MATHEMATICAL ENGAGEMENT OF GRADE 10 STUDENTS

MARY GRACEL. RETIRO¹

DELON A. CHING²

marygraceretiro@gmail.com¹

delon.ching@lspu.edu.ph²

0000-0003-1435-4371

Pacita Complex National High School, San Pedro, Laguna, Philippines¹

Laguna State Polytechnic University, San Pablo City, Laguna, Philippines²

ABSTRACT

Educational videos have become an important tool in mathematics education to contribute to the teaching-learning process especially in the current situation where distance learning was implemented throughout the nation. Educators must consider the cognitive load, video practices, and engaging elements of the videos to utilize the video effectively and ensure that learning and mathematical engagement take place. This study aims to determine the mathematical learning experiences using educational videos and mathematical engagement of Grade 10 students. The research design used a Descriptive and correlational design. The result of the study shows that the intrinsic, germane, and extraneous loads of the learning videos are often observed by the respondents. Mathematics teachers practiced considering signaling, segmenting, weeding, and matching modality using learning videos to students to which the engaging voice, pacing, length of the clip, and control of distractions are truly engaging. Moreover, the result showed a significant relationship between the Mathematical experiences using educational videos and the behavioral engagement of the students. It implies that educational videos helped students to achieve higher mathematical engagement and learning. The study recommends the creation of more educational videos to help students who are struggling in mathematics and to learn at their own pace during this time of distance learning. The study further recommends that the intrinsic load, length of clip, and control of distractions must be carefully studied in preparing educational learning videos for it predicts higher mathematical engagement of the students.

Keywords: Educational videos, Mathematical engagement, Distance learning